

The Effect of Dielectric Constant on Power Conversion Efficiency in P3HT-Based Organic and Hybrid Solar Cells

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Abstract

The primary aim of this study is to experimentally investigate the relationship between the dielectric constant of the active layer and the power conversion efficiency in P3HT-based organic and hybrid solar cells. I-V measurements were conducted for each solar cell produced using different mass ratios of P3HT and PCBM, with the highest power conversion efficiency calculated as 1.68%. The dielectric characterization of the solar cells was performed through capacitance measurements of the active layers, and the impact of the obtained dielectric constants on power conversion efficiency was analyzed. It was observed that charge separation is limited in organic solar cells due to their low dielectric constants, while cells with higher dielectric constants yield higher efficiencies. The results demonstrate that as the dielectric constant of the active layer increases, so does the efficiency of the solar cells. These findings provide valuable insights for enhancing the efficiency of organic and hybrid solar cells.

Keywords

Dielectric Constant
Hybrid Solar Cells
Organic Solar Cells
PCBM
Power Conversion Efficiency
P3HT

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for energy today is driven by a rapidly growing population, the formation of large urban centers, and advancements in technology. According to data from the International Energy Agency (IEA), which has 31 member countries including Turkey, global electricity output reached approximately 25,106 GWh in 2021 [1].

Energy experts project that by 2050, the world will require around 30 terawatts (TW) of energy resources to sustain economic growth [2].

Meeting this growing demand presents a significant challenge, for which organic solar cells offer a promising solution as they are clean, renewable, and cost-effective. Solar cells are photovoltaic devices that generate electricity by converting solar energy, and given the increasing interest worldwide in alternative energy sources, sunlight emerges as

an especially viable, clean, and abundant option compared to conventional fossil fuels.

Solar cells directly transform solar energy into electricity, and the potential energy from sunlight reaching Earth annually is approximately $3 \cdot 10^{24}$ J—about 10,000 times greater than the current global energy consumption. [3] Hypothetically, if just 0.1% of Earth's surface were covered with solar cells at an efficiency of 10%, it could meet global energy needs. Nevertheless, current solar cell-generated electricity accounts for less than 0.1% of the world's total energy consumption [4]. Solar cells are generally divided into three generations: the first generation, based on silicon wafers; the second generation, thin-film based; and the third generation, which includes organic structures [5]. Organic photovoltaic cells (OPVCs), a type of polymer solar cell, generate electricity from sunlight using flexible polymers. Although OPVCs have lower efficiency than inorganic cells due to their higher band

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gaps, they offer unique benefits. Traditional inorganic semiconductors, such as silicon, absorb a continuous light spectrum and possess a three-dimensional rigid lattice, which allows high carrier mobility. For instance, a silicon solar cell with a 1.1 eV bandgap (equivalent to a wavelength of 1100 nm) can reach a power conversion efficiency of 22% under AM1.5 conditions [6]. Conversely, the highest-performing polymer solar cells often use poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) as the donor material, which has a bandgap of 1.9 eV (650 nm), theoretically allowing it to capture up to 22.4% of available photons [7] and produce a maximum current density of 14.3 mA/cm² (see Table 1) and circumsolar(AM1.5D) as well as global (AM1.5G, ~ 1000 W/m²) solar irradiation available for a photovoltaic that harvest light from 280nm up to the wavelength, Assuming every photon converted into one electron in the external circuit [8].

Wavelength (nm)	Accumulated from 280 nm to the specified wavelength			
	Maximum harvested (%)		Current density (mA/cm ²)	
	AM1.5D	AM1.5G	AM1.5D	AM1.5G
500	8	9.4	5.1	6.5
550	12.5	14	8	9.7
600	17.3	19	11.1	13.2
650	22.4	24.3	14.3	16.8
700	27.6	29.6	17.6	20.4
750	32.6	34.7	20.8	23.9
800	37.3	39.5	23.8	27.2
900	46.7	48.8	29.8	33.7
1000	53	55	33.9	38
1100	61	62.9	39	43.4
1250	68.7	70.4	43.9	48.6
1500	75	76.5	47.9	52.8

Table 1. Values of The integrated photon flux and maximum current density from direct.

In combination with the widely-used acceptor material, [6,6]-phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM), the performance of a P3HT:PCBM system approaches an efficiency of around 5%, [9-13] which is less than a quarter of a silicon cell's optimal performance. Although OPVCs have lower efficiency, stability, and strength than inorganic counterparts—due to their susceptibility to oxygen and moisture—organic photovoltaic cells hold considerable potential due to their low production costs and molecular flexibility [14, 15].

Moreover, since the turn of the 21st century, advancements in both the efficiency of polymer photovoltaic

devices and understanding of the physical processes underlying OPVCs have significantly progressed [18]. Organic solar cells have recently reached a promising efficiency of 19.2% [16].

This study, titled “The Effect of Dielectric Constant on Power Conversion Efficiency in P3HT-Based Organic and Hybrid Solar Cells,” aims to produce organic and hybrid solar cells based on P3HT

, measure their dielectric constants, and investigate their power conversion efficiency. To achieve this, we will fabricate solar cells with P3HT and PCBM active layers that vary in dielectric constants and morphology. A highly efficient solar cell requires a high dielectric constant to promote charge separation by reducing Coulomb interactions between photo-excited electron-hole pairs.

Research on organic solar cell efficiency is relatively limited compared to that on inorganic cells, largely due to the low dielectric constants in organic cells. Additionally, few studies have examined how the dielectric constant influences power conversion efficiency. As a sustainable and environmentally friendly energy source, solar energy shows significant promise for addressing potential future energy crises. Organic solar cells, in particular, are notable for their suitability for flexible substrates, low production costs, and environmental advantages. Given these features, this study seeks to further understand the dielectric properties of organic solar cells and contribute to the enhancement of their efficiency.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, an ITO/PEDOT/P3HT:PCBM/Al solar cell was produced, as illustrated in Figure 1. P3HT (Poly(3-hexylthiophene)), a conjugated polymer, was used as the electron donor material for the solar cell. In the fabricated solar cells, PCBM ([6,6]-phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester) was used as the electron acceptor material, PEDOT:PSS as the hole transport layer, and pure aluminum (Al) elements were used as the bottom and top electrodes.

The PEDOT:PSS used in this study was purchased from H.C Starck, with a work function of approximately 5 eV. The P3HT, purchased from Rieke, has a HOMO of 5.2 eV and LUMO of 3.3 eV, while the PCBM from Solenbv has a HOMO level of 6.1 eV and a LUMO level of 4.2 eV.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of ITO/PEDOT:PSS/P3HT:PCBM/Al.

2.1. Cleaning of Glass Substrates

The first stage in the production of solar cells is cleaning the glass substrates. To achieve a high-efficiency solar cell, it is essential to thoroughly remove all contaminating atoms from the glass substrates. In this study, ITO-coated glass substrates with a thickness of 100 nm, dimensions of 1.5×1.5 cm, and a sheet resistance of 13Ω per square were used. To prevent short-circuiting of the ITO-coated glass, initially, as shown in Figure 2a, 2/3 of the substrate was covered with scotch tape, and the glass substrate was placed in an acid solution, allowing the ITO to be etched from the uncovered 1/3 area of the glass. During the experiment, it was observed that the capacity of the non-active ITO surface significantly affected the results. To eliminate this and obtain more accurate results, it was decided to enlarge the active area as much as possible, as shown in Figure 2b, where 4/5 of the ITO-coated glass was covered with tape, and 1/5 was etched.

Figure 2. (a) ITO glass with one-third etched (small active area), (b) ITO glass with one-fifth etched (large active area).

After covering the ITO-coated glasses with tape, the etching process was conducted: initially, the ITO-coated glasses were placed in an etching solution consisting of 250 ml of pure water, 230 ml of hydrochloric acid, and 20 ml of nitric acid for 30 minutes, during which the ITO on the 1/5 portion of the glass surface was etched away. Subsequently, the

glasses were removed from the acid solution, rinsed with pure water, and all surfaces were wiped with toluene after removing the tape. Following this, the glass substrates were subjected to a cleaning stage: each glass was placed sequentially in Helmanex solution, pure water, acetone, isopropanol, and finally pure water and cleaned in a BRANSON 3510 ultrasonic bath for 25 minutes in each solution. During cleaning, the glasses were rinsed in a beaker of pure water before progressing to the next step to remove residues from previous steps. Finally, the cleaned glasses were dried using high-purity dry air.

2.2. Formation of Active Layer Films

After the glass substrates were cleaned, the ITO-coated glass surfaces were first coated with PEDOT: PSS which was used as the hole transport layer. At this stage, PEDOT: PSS was applied evenly onto the surface using a $40 \mu\text{m}$ Whatman filter and subsequently placed in a spin coater at 1500 rpm for 10 seconds and 2000 rpm for 40 seconds for uniform distribution. The etched area of the glass opposite the previously etched section was wiped with water-soaked cotton to remove PEDOT: PSS. Subsequently, the PEDOT: PSS glasses were dried on a hot plate at 140°C for 20 minutes.

An active layer was then deposited on the PEDOT: PSS glasses using the spin coating technique. The procedure for preparing P3HT solutions was as follows: 6 mg of P3HT and 4 mg of PCBM were precisely weighed and dissolved in 500 mL of chlorobenzene in a light-protected bottle containing a magnetic stirrer, and the solution was stirred for 20 hours. 50 μL of the P3HT: PCBM solution was then evenly pipetted onto the PEDOT: PSS surface and spin-coated at 1000 rpm. Afterward, the opposite side of the etched area was cleaned with toluene-soaked cotton to remove P3HT: PCBM. This cleaning step prevents the negative electrode from contacting the active area after electrode deposition, thus avoiding a short circuit.

2.3. Film Thickness Measurement and Surface Morphology of Solar Cells

To determine the surface morphology of the coated films and measure the film thickness, a Park System XE 70 atomic force microscope (AFM) was used, as illustrated in Figure 3 for the surface morphology of the P3HT: PCBM active layer.

The film thickness was measured by stripping a portion of the film with toluene and calculating the thickness difference between the stripped and coated areas. Figures 4a and 4b show the method used for thickness measurement, yielding an approximate film thickness of 75 nm for the P3HT: PCBM active layer.

Figure 3. AFM image of the P3HT:PCBM sample.

Figure 4a: AFM image taken during film thickness measurement.

Figure 4b: AFM image taken during film thickness measurement.

Finally, the solar cells with coated active layers were placed on a specialized mask (shown in Figure 5) for Al electrode deposition and were subsequently placed in a UNIVEX 300 vacuum deposition system, where they were coated with approximately 100 nm thick Al electrodes under a pressure of 1.6×10^{-5} mbar. The film thickness was measured using the INFICO XTM2 Deposition Monitor on the vacuum coating system.

Figure 5. Mask and electrode-coated solar cells placed inside the vacuum deposition system.

2.4. I-V Characterization of Solar Cells

In this study, to determine the characteristic parameters of the solar cells, such as open-circuit voltage (VOC), short-circuit current (ISC), fill factor (FF), and maximum power point (Pmax), and subsequently calculate the power conversion efficiency (η), I-V characterization was performed on each cell. During these measurements, the solar cells were illuminated under AM 1.5 light using a Solar Light XPS 150 solar simulator, and I-V curves were obtained between -1V initial voltage and +1V final voltage using a KEITHLEY 2612B SMU.

2.5. I-V Dielectric Characterization of Solar Cells

To investigate the effect of the dielectric constant of solar cells on power conversion efficiency, the capacitance (C) of each fabricated solar cell was measured using a HIOKI 3522-50 LCR HiTESTER at frequencies between 1 and 100 Hz. The parallel capacitor structure of the ITO-coated layer and active area is schematically illustrated in Figure 8. The capacitance (Cd) measured during dielectric characterization is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Schematic representation of ITO and the active layer behaving like two parallel capacitors.

The experimentally measured C_d value is given by Equation 1.1:

$$C_d = C_0 + C \quad (1.1)$$

where C_0 is the capacitance of the ITO layer and C is the capacitance of the active layer. To obtain the dielectric constant of the active layer, Equation 1.1 is solved for

$$C = C_d - C_0 \quad (1.2)$$

Substituting values for C_d and C_0 gives:

$$\kappa \epsilon_0 \frac{A_3}{d} = C_d - \epsilon_0 \frac{A_0}{d} \quad (1.3)$$

If equation 1.3 is solved for κ :

$$\kappa = \frac{d \cdot C_d}{\epsilon_0 A_3} - \frac{A_0}{A_3} \quad (1.4)$$

Where κ represents the dielectric constant of the active layer, ϵ_0 , is the permittivity of vacuum, A_3 , is the area of the active layer, A_0 is the average area, and d is the distance between the plates or the thickness of the active layer film.

3. Results and Discussion

The solar cells with P3HT:PCBM active layers were named XA-16 and XA-19. The I-V graphs for these cells are shown in Figures 7 and 8, respectively.

Figure 7. I-V curve of the XA-16 solar cell.

Figure 8. I-V curve of the XA-19 solar cell.

The characteristic parameters and power conversion efficiencies of the XA-16 and XA-19 solar cells are summarized in Table 2. The capacitance versus frequency

graphs of XA-16 and XA-19 are displayed in Figures 11 and 12, respectively, while the spectrum of their dielectric constants is shown in Figure 11.

Cell Name	V _{oc} (V)	I _{sc} (mA)	Fill Factor (FF)	Area (mm ²)	Efficiency (η)
XA-16	0,63	2,67	0,37	61,39	%1,03
XA-19	0,59	2,92	0,44	45,2	%1,68

Table 2: Characteristic parameters and power conversion efficiencies of the XA-16 and XA-19 solar cells.

Figure 9: Frequency-capacitance graph of the XA-16 solar cell.

Figure 10: Frequency-capacitance graph of the XA-19 solar cell.

Figure 11: Dielectric spectrum graph of the XA-16 and XA-19 solar cells.

4. Conclusions

In organic solar cells, photocurrent generation occurs when excitons, formed in the donor-acceptor region, dissociate and collect at the relevant electrodes as free charge carriers. Therefore, merely increasing the number of excitons at the donor-acceptor interface is not sufficient to enhance the power conversion efficiency. For power conversion efficiency to increase, these excitons, bound to each other by a binding energy, must also dissociate. The dissociation of excitons in an organic solar cell depends on the dielectric properties and the dielectric constant of the environment. To facilitate the dissociation of excitons at the donor-acceptor interface by the internal electric field, a high dielectric constant in the environment is required. The external electric field applied to the dielectric environment polarizes the dielectric material, and as a result of this polarization, the electric field is shielded by the dielectric environment. This study was initiated with the assumption that a high dielectric constant (κ) in the active layer would directly reflect on the efficiency.

In this context, hybrid solar cells with an ITO/PEDOT/P3HT:PCBM/Al structure were fabricated, and their photovoltaic parameters were measured. The I-V characterization of each produced solar cell was performed, and power conversion efficiencies were calculated. The highest power conversion efficiency achieved was calculated as 1.68%. By experimentally measuring the capacitance of the active areas of the solar cells, dielectric constants were calculated, and the relationship between the dielectric constant

of the active areas of the solar cells and their power conversion efficiencies constituted the main topic of this study.

Previous studies have shown that solar cells produced with the same active layer and under the same production conditions never exhibit identical efficiency. The primary reason for this is the difference in morphology, i.e., the molecular arrangement, of each solar cell, which leads to differences in dipole moment densities within the structure. This difference results in variations in the dielectric constant of the active layer of each solar cell, which directly affects efficiency.

High dielectric constants were measured in the low-frequency range (1–10 Hz) for all solar cells. The reason for the high dielectric constant in this frequency range is due to polarization. In the low-frequency region, the applied external electric field provides a long time for the dipoles to orient themselves in the direction of the electric field, which results in a high dielectric constant value.

As shown in Figure 11, the solar cell with a higher efficiency among those produced with a P3HT:PCBM active layer also has a higher dielectric constant for its active layer. This systematic finding demonstrates that the reason behind the different efficiencies in solar cells produced under identical conditions is the dielectric constant of the active layer.

To conduct more sensitive studies on the effect of the dielectric constant on efficiency, it is necessary to use a solar cell geometry where the electrodes are entirely identical. However, this also introduces the risk of short-circuiting the electrodes. Therefore, different techniques need to be explored to produce a solar cell where the electrodes will not touch each

other but will be nearly identical. This can be considered as an advanced study to follow up on this paper.

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